

1 **DEVELOPMENT OF A COST EFFECTIVE PASSIVE SAMPLER TO QUANTIFY THE PARTICULATE**
2 **MATTER DEPOSITIONS ON BUILDING MATERIALS OVER TIME**

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12
13 **ABSTRACT**

14 Air pollution represents a serious risk for the preservation of open-air Cultural Heritage. In the
15 past, the attention of researchers was focused mainly on the role of gaseous pollutants on stone
16 or mortar deteriorations; however, the huge increase in automobile traffic has promoted a
17 considerable rise in the levels of ozone, nitrogen oxides and Particulate Matter (PM). PM
18 depositions may contribute to trigger the sulphating process of porous building materials and to
19 add new ions, which may react and change the original composition of the materials. Because
20 of this, the knowledge of PM composition near monuments or buildings over time is becoming
21 an important issue in conservation strategies. In this work, a simple and cost-efficient passive
22 sampler is proposed to quantify the PM being deposited over building material surfaces per area
23 and time of exposure. The passive sampler described in this work, consisting on retainers
24 specially designed for XRF analysis, is used for the first time as a simple way for characterising
25 the surrounding atmospheric contamination caused by PM, without the need of other
26 commonly employed more expensive PM active samplers such as cascade impactors. The
27 particles trapped in this way can then be easily analysed by means of Scanning Electron
28 Microscopy coupled to Energy Dispersive Spectrometer (SEM-EDS), Micro Energy Dispersive X-
29 Ray Fluorescence Spectrometry (μ -EDXRF) and Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry
30 (ICP-MS). The PM passive sampler and the characterisation methodology proposed in this work
31 can be extensively applied to other situations where PM characterisation is required.

32
33 **INTRODUCTION**

34 Air pollution represents a serious risk for the preservation of Cultural Heritage, particularly
35 for buildings, open-air monuments and archaeological sites located nearby cities, industries or
36 commercial ports. [1,2] Especially, historical buildings are the most susceptible to this
37 deterioration because they are usually located in city centres directly exposed to high
38 concentrations of atmospheric pollutants. Therefore, their conservation is correlated to the
39 impact of such pollutants. In this sense, the monitoring of pollutants and their surface deposition
40 are crucial for Cultural Heritage preservation.

41 In the past, the attention of researchers was focused mainly on the role of gaseous pollutants
42 on stone or mortar deteriorations, especially on sulphur dioxide. [1] However, in many areas of
43 Europe, the levels of SO₂ have been reduced while the huge increase in automobile traffic has

44 promoted a considerable rise in the levels of ozone, nitrogen oxides and Particulate Matter (PM).
45 [3,4] Aerosol derived from combustion processes is also recognised to be the main cause of
46 atmospheric pollution in urban environments after gaseous contamination. [5] Iron and steel
47 industries are considered another important source of PM emission. [6] Among the constituents
48 of PM, it has been observed an increase in carbonaceous and nitrogenous fractions. All this has
49 generated a completely new air pollution scenario. [1] Carbonaceous particles are not only the
50 cause of the blackening of building façades, which damage the appearance of them, [7] but they
51 also play an active role in calcite sulphating processes due to their ability to accelerate the rate
52 of fixation of atmospheric SO₂ to form gypsum (black crust formations). [8,9] The presence of
53 metallic particles in the atmospheric PM can also trigger this process. [8] Moreover, their high
54 specific surface (10- 100 m²/g) converts them into a catalytic support for deterioration reactions.
55 [10] The presence of abundant C- and Fe-rich particles coming from diesel vehicles has been
56 demonstrated to play a critical role in the oxidation of SO₂ and the formation of H₂SO₄, which is
57 the main responsible of the sulphating processes. [11]

58 Although the implication of air pollution on buildings deterioration is well-known, studies of
59 atmospheric pollutant monitoring close to monuments remain rare and the few cases reported
60 in literature are mostly devoted to the study and control of the indoor environments. [12–15]
61 Furthermore, in most of the cases, the indoor monitoring consists only on Temperature, Relative
62 Humidity (RH) and CO₂ for the study of biological proliferation or the favouring of efflorescences
63 and sub-efflorescences. [12,16,17] There are some works also dealing with the study of PM
64 affecting the art objects in the indoor environment of museums. [18–20] However, very little
65 work has been performed to asses and monitor the impact of air pollution on historic buildings
66 with the aim of protecting them from damage.

67 The characteristics of such atmospheres must be evaluated in the framework of a
68 rehabilitation process, defining all the chemical compounds that can potentially interact with
69 the materials in the different surfaces of the buildings. However, most of the works related with
70 the monitoring of pollutants in urban areas have been performed with the aim to study their
71 effect on human health. [21–24] In this sense, the monitoring is generally assessed according to
72 the air quality directives for the protection of human health. [25] The resulting data often
73 regards samples collected far away from the monument or building of interest and thus, do not
74 allow the evaluation of the spatial and temporal variations of multi-pollutants in the proximity
75 to the monuments or buildings to be protected.

76 The existence of air pollution monitoring stations, belonging to a public entity, in the
77 surroundings of the building under study helps in the characterisation of some chemicals, such
78 as CO₂, SO₂, NO_x, or Particulate matter (PM₁₀ and/or PM_{2.5}). Moreover, the time series that are
79 usually available for such stations give us the required information to check seasonal variabilities
80 that must be considered to perform the adequate characterisation of the atmosphere around
81 the building. Unfortunately, those monitoring stations do not give the chemical composition of
82 PM. The knowledge of particle composition near monuments or buildings over time is becoming
83 an important issue in conservation strategies and several works have already been carried out.
84 [1,26] Commonly, deposition of PM is related with traffic, industrial/urban fog and/or marine
85 aerosol in the coastal areas. [26]

86 The sampling and collection of PM can be performed with different methods. Inertial
87 collectors are the most employed ones to give a size-representative sample of particles
88 suspended in the atmosphere. [27] In general terms, these sampling methods are expensive and
89 require regular maintenance. [26] In addition, for the study of the effect of PM deposition on
90 monuments and buildings, it is not indispensable a separation of PM by size. In fact, there are
91 other possibilities to characterise PM, which do not imply PM collector instrumentation and can
92 give information about the kind of PM pollution of the surrounding environment of the
93 building/monument and thus, their influence on the degradation. There are works dealing with
94 self-made passive samplers [26,28] or even with natural passive samplers growing over the
95 building façades due to their chemical degradation, black crusts, [29] or to biofilms. [30]
96 However, the information obtained from these natural passive samplers can be somehow
97 limited. On the one hand, because they simply are not present in the place of study and on the
98 other hand, when quantification and/or temporal trends are needed, because the matrix is
99 unknown and complex, and the time of exposure is also unknown. In order to control these
100 parameters, artificially controlled passive samplers are needed.

101 In this work, a cost-efficient and easy to assemble passive sampler has been developed to
102 quantify the PM being deposited over building materials per area and time of exposure. The
103 passive sampler developed in this work, as an alternative to commercial PM samplers, consists
104 on an assembly of adsorbent retainers specially dedicated to X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis.
105 Considering that the filter inserted in the retainer represents an appropriate blank for elemental
106 analysis, the particles trapped were analysed directly by means of Scanning Electron Microscopy
107 coupled to Energy Dispersive Spectrometer (SEM-EDS), Micro Energy Dispersive XRF
108 spectrometry (μ -EDXRF) and Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS). The
109 applicability of this PM passive sampler was verified to study the PM arriving to the building
110 materials of a historical construction, the Galleries of Punta Begoña (Getxo, North of Spain),
111 located in front of the sea in a highly dense urban area with the influence of a commercial port.
112 This new PM passive sampler will allow to extract information about not only the atmospheric
113 PM contamination, but also about the kind of particles that can impact on the built heritage.

114

115 **EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE**

116 **Sampling site**

117 The monument under study is the Galleries of Punta Begoña. The building was erected in
118 1918, on the top of a cliff that hosted the first defensive fortification (1645) of the estuary of
119 Bilbao (North of Spain), the Punta Begoña Fortress, whose remains are probably into the
120 architectural complex of the Galleries. This building has been subjected to different impacts
121 caused by the industrial evolution, over the last 100 years, in the industrial-port area of Bilbao
122 (exhaust from ships and traffic, mineral dusts from discharges, gases from a refinery, PM from
123 an old and a new power station, different metallurgical and chemical factories, etc.), together
124 with the influence of the marine aerosols and humans (graffitists and vandalism).

125

126 **Passive sampler and samplings description**

127 With the aim to design a passive sampler that allows a fast and direct characterisation of PM
128 with the μ -EDXRF spectrometer, special retainers for X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis, Rigaku
129 Ultra Carry Light sample retainers (Rigaku, Tokyo, Japan) were used as sorbent surfaces. These
130 retainers are composed of an external PET ring, which holds a polyester film where a special
131 cellulose adsorbent filter is fixed, especially designed for depositing and retaining liquids (see
132 Figure S-1 A). [31] The retainers were stuck with adhesive to a wooden plank previously lined
133 with Mylar to prevent the adsorbents from possible contaminations. The wooden plank was
134 placed in Punta Begoña Galleries, on the wall of the Lower Gallery directly oriented to the ports
135 of Getxo. A picture of the sampling device inside the Galleries can be seen in Figure S-1 B from
136 Supplementary Material.

137 Sample retainers were extracted from the plank every month during the first 5 months of
138 exposure and then, every two months until a total of 11 months of exposure. In each sampling
139 campaign, three retainers randomly picked up from the wooden plank were collected in order
140 to have different replicates for each exposed period of time and not to be conditioned by the
141 location of the filter on the wall. The adsorbents were collected and transported inside two petri
142 glasses of different size, building in this way a glass box, in order to avoid any kind of contact
143 with the surface of the retainers where the particles were trapped. It must be pointed out that
144 the collected retainers on the 11th month were deteriorated due to the wind action. Therefore,
145 it was not possible to extract any information from the 11th month, thus being the ones collected
146 after 9 months the last retainers considered in this work.

147

148 **Instrumentation**

149 The exposed retainers were firstly analysed by means of a JEOL JSM-7000-F SEM (JEOL, Tokio,
150 Japan) SEM-EDS (Oxford instruments INCA, Energy 350, Oxfordshire, UK). The elemental spectra
151 were collected at 20 kV and 1 mA at low vacuum. In order to improve the conductivity of the
152 samples, the retainers were firstly metalized by depositing approximately 20 μ m of carbon. The
153 element assignation was performed with the INCA software (Oxford Instruments, Oxfordshire,
154 UK).

155 The XRF measurements were performed using a M4 TORNADO EDXRF spectrometer (Bruker
156 Nano GmbH, Germany) provided with two Rh X-ray tubes powered by low-power HV generators
157 and cooled by air. In this work, the tube working between 10- 50 kV and 100- 600 μ A and
158 connected to a poly-capillary system that allows to work under a lateral/spatial resolution of 25
159 μ m measured for Mo K α (around 17 mm at 2.3 keV to 32 μ m at 18.3 keV) was used. In each
160 cellulose filter, a square area of 33 x 33 mm² was mapped always encompassing completely the
161 exposed filter and only leaving without mapping the rigid PET ring. The step size between each
162 measurement point was always 20 μ m, with a measuring time of 3 ms for each point and using
163 a single scan. All the measurements were performed under vacuum to improve the detection of
164 light elements. In order to be able to compare the non-invasively obtained results with the ones
165 obtained afterwards by ICP-MS (destructive method), a circular area of 800 mm² corresponding
166 to the whole adsorbent surface of the retainer without the rigid PET ring was selected and the
167 concentrations of the detected elements from the sum spectrum of the whole mapping were
168 obtained using a quantification method based on Fundamental Parameters. In this sense, it is
169 necessary to point out that the used method is not specific for the analysed matrix, thus the
170 obtained concentrations should be considered semi-quantitative.

171 In order to measure elements with concentrations under the Limit of Detection (LOD) or
172 under the Limit of Quantification (LOQ) in EDXRF, a microwave assisted acid extraction using 3:1
173 HNO₃ (69%)-HCl (36%) of the 800 mm² circular area (this area can be easily detached from the
174 rigid PET ring) was carried out followed by ICP-MS quantification of these extracts. The
175 quantification was performed using a NexION 300 ICP-MS (Perkin Elmer, Ontario, Canada)
176 working in a class 100 clean room. ²⁷Al, ⁴⁴Ca, ⁸⁸Sr, ¹³⁸Ba, and ²⁰⁶⁺²⁰⁷⁺²⁰⁸Pb isotopes were
177 determined in standard mode and ²³Na, ²⁴Mg, ³⁹K, ⁴⁷Ti, ⁵¹V, ⁵²Cr, ⁵⁵Mn, ⁵⁶Fe, ⁵⁹Co, ⁶⁰Ni, ⁶⁵Cu, ⁶⁶Zn,
178 isotopes were determined in collision mode with He, in order to eliminate possible polyatomic
179 interferences. The plasma conditions such as nebulizer argon flow, torch position and
180 instrument lenses voltages were firstly optimized before each measurement session by
181 aspirating a standard solution of 1 ng/mL of Mg, Rh, In, Ba, Pb and U. The gas nebulizer flow was
182 optimized for a compromise between sensitivity and low oxides level (less than 2.5 % for the
183 CeO/Ce ratio). Before the measurement of the acid extracts, their acid concentration had to be
184 reduced to 1% of HNO₃ by dilution with Milli-Q water. Finally, the data treatment was performed
185 with the NexION 1.5 software (Perkin Elmer, Ontario, Canada). A non-exposed filter to the
186 environment was also subjected to the same procedure as the blank sample.

187

188 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

189 Scanning Electron Microscopy- Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy characterisation

190 The retainers collected the last months (7 months of exposure), and thus expected to present
191 the highest amount of retained particles, were metallized with carbon and analysed under the
192 SEM-EDS instrument. In Figure 1, a SEM microphotograph of the PM retainers is displayed
193 showing the cellulose filaments composing the filter of the retainer and the particles attached
194 to it. Different elemental analyses of some of the particles retained are also collected in Figure
195 1. This analysed area is very representative of the whole analysis performed also in other filters
196 exposed for longer or shorter times, with the only difference in the amount of particles trapped.

197 In this area, the biggest particles are mainly composed of Ca, S and O (see Figure 1, S-1 and
198 S2), probably due to the presence of gypsum, a kind of particle also detected in previous works
199 carried out in the same building by Morillas et al. [28] In some cases, Al and Si are also found
200 probably due to the deposition of aluminosilicates (see Figure 1, S-2 and S-4), widely present in
201 every atmosphere. The spectrum S-3 from Figure 1 represents the measurement performed on
202 a single particle, showing the main presence of Ca and S (less intense signals than in S-1 and S-
203 2), and Na and Cl. According to this experimental evidence, this kind of particle can be related
204 with the presence of NaCl together with CaSO₄ (without or without water molecules) or to the
205 presence of the mixed salt NaCaClSO₄, suggested in the previous work performed by Morillas *et*
206 *al.* [28]

207 On the other hand, the smallest bright particles correspond in most of the cases to Fe
208 particles (see Figure 1, S-5 to S-7). In some of these particles, Fe is present together with other
209 metals such as Cr, Mn (see Figure 1, S-5) or Cu and Zn (see Figure 1, S-7). All the metallic particles
210 have a diameter lower than 5 μm, and in most of the cases the common sizes are set around 2-
211 5 μm. In S-7, Fe seems to be related to Cl, which may suggest the presence of iron chlorides.

212

213 Figure 1. SEM microphotograph of the PM retainer showing the particles trapped on it and the
 214 representative EDS spectra acquired in some of these particles.

215

216 **Micro Energy-Dispersive X-ray Fluorescence characterisation to evaluate the temporal**
 217 **evolution of atmospheric PM deposition**

218 In Figure 2, some elemental imaging analysis for the major elements, trapped in one of the
 219 PM retainers exposed for 9 months are shown as an example. Through μ-EDXRF imaging, it was

220 possible to confirm the high presence of calcium sulphate particles in the area where the passive
221 sampler was exposed (see the Ca and S coincident distribution in Figure 2). This result agrees
222 with the previous observation extracted by SEM-EDS.

223

224 Figure 2. A) 33 x 33 mm² square mapped area in the whole PM retainer; B) Mapped area of
225 PM retainer and some elemental distributions measured in one of the replicates of the PM
226 filter exposed for 9 months in Punta Begoña (X9C).

227 Apart from the wide distribution of Cl, coming from the influence of marine aerosol, in the
228 acquired maps (see Figure 2), other particles such as Si are also highly present. Si can be related
229 with the presence of quartz or other silicates coming from the impact of the sand carried by the
230 wind coming from the nearby beach.

231 Among the metals, Fe particles were the more widely distributed ones on the retainers. Fe
232 particles can be emitted as a consequence of different industrial and metallurgical processes,
233 shipping, combustion of fossil fuels, diesel emissions, tyre and break wear and other traffic
234 emissions if iron compounds were added as catalysts in engines. [32] Fe particles can also come
235 from the resuspension of crustal material. [32] The Galleries, where the passive sampler was
236 installed, are in a highly industrialised area, in front of an industrial port with an important

237 shipping activity and they are just above of a very busy road especially in the summer period.
238 Together with Fe, Zn was also present in the trapped particles. Zn may be also coming from tyre
239 dust, as zinc oxide is added as an activator during the vulcanizing process of the tyre, being up
240 to 4.3% of the resulting tyre tread. [33] Cu, Ti and Mn were also found in some of the retainers,
241 but at low concentrations close to their LOQ in ED-XRF. Cu can also be part of the mentioned
242 tyre dust as well as Mn, but Cu is especially important in brake dust. [33]

243 Apart from the determination of the qualitative elemental composition of the trapped
244 particles and their distribution in the retainer, the concentration of each element coming from
245 the particles trapped in the retainers was approached through μ -EDXRF. With this aim, once
246 each retainer is mapped, the filter area of the retainer, where the particles are trapped is
247 selected from the mapping (see the selected circular area of 800 mm² in Figure S-2 from
248 Supplementary Material). Afterwards, the sum spectrum of the selected area can be obtained.
249 This spectrum represents the counts given by all the elements present as a whole in the selected
250 area. Therefore, this spectrum can be used to extract the concentration of each element present
251 in the selected area.

252 Considering that for the quantification of the PM, a quantification method based on
253 Fundamental Parameters (FP), not specifically designed for the PM trapped on the retainers was
254 used, only a semi-quantification was able to be conducted, instead of a quantification in the
255 strict sense. The employed method only includes the information of the elements detected in
256 the retainer and no-additional matrix corrections could be carried out. First, three filters without
257 being exposed to the atmosphere were measured as blanks to obtain the background
258 concentrations of the detectable elements in the non-exposed retainers. The blanks were
259 mapped using the same conditions as the ones employed for the exposed retainers and the
260 same 800 mm² circular area was selected to obtain the elemental concentrations on the exposed
261 surfaces. In Table S-1 from Supplementary Material, the mean elemental concentrations with
262 their corresponding standard deviations for the three cellulose filter blanks are summarised. In
263 this table, only the elements above the LOD of the EDXRF for the blanks are shown. The
264 concentrations obtained in the blank were subtracted from those obtained in the exposed filters
265 and then, were used to obtain deposition tendencies.

266 In Figure 3, some tendencies for the elements detected in the PM retainers are shown. In
267 these graphics, the mean elemental concentrations obtained for three different PM retainers
268 collected in the same day together with their corresponding standard deviations are shown
269 against the time of exposure. As can be appreciated, all of them present an expected increasing
270 tendency over time, although some of the elements (e.g., Na, Cl, Mg, Al and Si) seem to achieve
271 the saturation in the filter after the first six months of exposure. The mean value seems to be a
272 little bit lower in the last measured month (9 months of exposure). However, considering the
273 standard deviations, the concentrations are more or less in the same interval. On the other hand,
274 S, Ca and Fe concentrations keep increasing during the period of 9 months studied in this work.

275 Another observation that could be highlighted is the extremely similar tendency observed
276 for Al and Si, which may suggest again the presence of aluminosilicate depositions.
277 Aluminosilicates are present in the dust of the atmosphere but also in the fine-grained
278 sediments deposited in the nearby beach sands. In the same way, the tendencies of Ca and S

279 are similar due probably to the presence of calcium sulphate particles. Cu and Zn signals were
280 perfectly distinguishable in the spectra, but they were under the limit of quantification.

281

282 Figure 3. EDXRF elemental concentrations expressed in mg/kg obtained by Fundamental
283 Parameters of the exposed PM retainers vs different exposure times expressed in months.

284

285 Inductively Couple Plasma Mass Spectrometry quantification of the rate of metal impact on 286 the walls of Punta Begoña Galleries

287 In order to measure the elements with concentrations under the LOD or under the LOQ of
288 the μ -EDXRF methodology, an acid extraction of the 800 mm² circular area was carried out to
289 subsequently quantify the extracted elements by ICP-MS.

290 In this case, after determining the concentration of the elements in the acid extract, the
291 mass of each element in the extract and by extension in the extracted filter area was calculated.
292 Then, the total elemental mass was divided by the 800 mm² of retention surface. The ng/cm²
293 values were also divided by the exposure time, obtaining in this way, not only the mass
294 deposited per area, but also per month of exposure. Moreover, a mean value was also calculated
295 for mass deposition per area and per time of exposure, even though the deviations of the
296 predicted values can be considered high, because the mass deposition will depend highly on the
297 month due to different weather conditions, anthropogenic activities, etc. Usually, this
298 parameter requires complicate mathematical models [34–36] to be calculated. In this case, using
299 simple retainers and their subsequent analysis by ICP-MS, these values can be approached in a
300 realistic way. The mentioned values are presented in Tables 1 to 4. In all the cases the blank
301 concentrations are already subtracted.

302 As can be observed, the concentrations obtained by ICP-MS are not comparable with the
303 ones calculated in the retainers using the EDXRF FP-method, since in this case, a totally
304 quantitative methodology has been developed. In addition, the ED-XRF measurements give the

305 concentration of the elements trapped on the surface, and the difference in mass between the
 306 non-exposed and the exposed retainers is not possible to be measured with an analytical
 307 balance to obtain the absolute mass trapped on the retainers as with ICP-MS.

308 The highest concentrations were associated to Ca, and Na. The first element can be related
 309 to the presence of calcium sulfates and also to a calcareous origin, due to the erosion of nearby
 310 calcium carbonate rocks. The high presence of Na can be related to the influence of the marine
 311 aerosol.

312 As can be observed in Tables 1 to 4, the elemental concentrations for most of the elements
 313 (Li, Na, Mg, K, Ti, Mn, Sr and Pb) follow the same increasing tendency with the time of exposure
 314 (see ng/cm²) as previously observed with the μ -EDXRF analysis. Some of the elements (e.g., Na,
 315 Mg and Ca) also present the same saturation tendency in the last month.

316

317 **Table 1. Deposited mass per area and per time calculated for Li, Na and Mg determined by ICP-MS.**

Exposure time (months)	Li		Na		Mg	
	ng/cm ²	ng/cm ² /month	ng/cm ²	ng/cm ² /month	ng/cm ²	ng/cm ² /month
2	0.110	0.055	2155	1078	242	121
3	0.314	0.105	6990	2330	725	242
4	0.228	0.057	11022	2756	1148	287
5	0.406	0.081	14150	2830	1486	297
7	0.626	0.089	17632	2519	1870	267
9	0.941	0.104	16741	1860	1852	206
Mean		0.08 ± 0.02	Mean	(2.2 ± 0.7)·10⁴	Mean	(2.4 ± 0.6)·10²

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319

320 **Table 2. Deposited mass per area and per time calculated for Al, K and Ca determined by ICP-MS.**

Exposure time (months)	Al		K		Ca	
	ng/cm ²	ng/cm ² /month	ng/cm ²	ng/cm ² /month	ng/cm ²	ng/cm ² /month
2	217	108	93	46	1059	529
3	407	136	230	76	1824	608
4	309	77	364	91	1202	300
5	414	83	466	93	3095	619
7	534	76	581	83	4698	671
9	728	81	586	65	4322	480
Mean		90 ± 20	Mean	70 ± 20	Mean	(5 ± 1)·10²

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Table 3. Deposited mass per area and per time calculated for Ti, Mn and Fe determined by ICP-MS.

Exposure time (months)	Ti		Mn		Fe	
	ng/cm ²	ng/cm ² /month	ng/cm ²	ng/cm ² /month	ng/cm ²	ng/cm ² /month
2	2.01	1.00	0.95	0.48	x	X
3	3.61	1.20	9.07	3.02	x	X
4	5.47	1.37	12.5	3.12	x	X
5	8.21	1.64	18.4	3.69	304	61
7	12.7	1.81	29.3	4.18	103	15
9	16.0	1.77	72.09	8.01	511	57
Mean		1.5 ± 0.3	Mean	4 ± 2	Mean	40 ± 20

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Table 4. Deposited mass per area and per time calculated for Sr, Ba and Pb determined by ICP-MS.

Exposure time (months)	Sr		Ba		Pb	
	ng/cm ²	ng/cm ² /month	ng/cm ²	ng/cm ² /month	ng/cm ²	ng/cm ² /month
2	3.99	1.99	1.51	0.75	2.05	1.02
3	9.40	3.13	5.08	1.69	3.47	1.16
4	12.0	3.01	2.00	0.49	7.25	1.81
5	16.4	3.29	7.78	1.56	13.2	2.63
7	21.4	3.06	6.67	0.95	13.8	1.97
9	24.3	2.70	33.1	3.68	14.8	1.65
Mean		2.9 ± 0.5	Mean	2 ± 1	Mean	1.7 ± 0.6

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In this case and considering the lower LOQ achievable for heavy elements by ICP-MS, Pb and Ba, elements not previously detected by μ -EDXRF, were quantified. However, other elements such as Zn, Cr and Cu were below the LOQ except for the last month, where concentrations slightly higher than the ones detected in the blank were obtained. This same fact was commented before in the analysis of EDXRF results.

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The concentrations of Ca, Ba and Al present the same increasing tendency with time, except in the filter exposed for 4 months, which is in all the cases, a little bit low. For Al and Ca measured by means of EDXRF, this was not observed for the mean value of the three filters collected after 4 months of exposure. This could be related with the presence of aluminosilicates that may not have been completely digested before the ICP-MS measurement. Therefore, an incomplete acid extraction could be affecting to the quantification of Al, K and Ca especially. It must also be highlighted that the acid extraction and ICP-MS determination shows that acidic soluble Fe is under the LOQ for the retainers collected during the first four months of exposure. This tendency was not observed in the EDXRF results. Thus, the Fe detected in the first five months could be related to insoluble silicate compounds, while the obtained after the five months could have both contributions, the insoluble silicate compounds containing iron and the iron particles that can be digested in the acidic treatment. Moreover, the measurement of a blank performed only with acids and without adding the retainer, showed a negligible contribution of Fe in comparison to the contribution of Fe coming from the non-exposed retainers.

350 The Fe concentration detected after 9 months of exposure is clearly above the LOQ, obtaining
351 the highest concentration (57 ng/cm²/month) of all the metals deposited on the retainers. The
352 non-detection of soluble Fe in the first months of exposure could be related with the irregular
353 activity of the anthropogenic emission sources, which contribute with the emission of the
354 soluble iron related to PM. The contributions of Pb, Ba, Ti and Mn are much lower, thus showing
355 again the principal metal deposition of Fe nowadays.

356

357 CONCLUSIONS

358 In this work, a retainer especially designed for XRF analyses was tested as a candidate to trap
359 PM and thus, to be used as a passive sampler in order to evaluate the composition of the PM in
360 the atmosphere and their impact on building materials from historical constructions. To verify
361 this, a proper multianalytical methodology was developed. In a first step, non-invasive analysis
362 of the retainers was conducted. Thanks to SEM-EDS, it was possible to firstly, evaluate the
363 capacity of these retainers to trap particles and it allowed us to determine the nature of
364 individual or cluster particles too. On the other hand, μ -EDXRF spectrometry following an
365 imaging strategy, allowed to determine the nature of the main elements constituting the
366 particles trapped and their distribution on the retainers without any previous pre-treatment of
367 the retainers.

368 In a second step, applying a destructive analysis of the retainers through ICP-MS, an idea of
369 the amount of ng of element deposited per area and time of exposure was obtained. In this way,
370 the deposition flux of PM can be obtained, which is a very interesting data when talking about
371 the effect of PM deposition affecting a building. In addition, some elements (e.g., Pb and Ba)
372 under the LOQ of the μ -EDXRF methodology could be detected using ICP-MS due to its better
373 sensitivity.

374 Although ICP-MS allows to improve the LOQ in comparison with μ -ED-XRF technique, it is
375 important to remark some advantages of the latter. The first one is the ability to perform direct
376 non-invasive measurements, avoiding the acid extraction step. Second, it can provide
377 information about the presence of Si, S and Cl. In this case, it was not possible to determine the
378 presence of S and Cl by ICP-MS. The high first ionization potential of S leads to a relatively low
379 ionization efficiency in an argon-based plasma. [37] In addition, S is quite light element and thus,
380 it is not transmitted by common ion optics as effectively as heavier elements. [37] Finally, S
381 detection is also hampered by spectral interferences formed inside the plasma, mainly due to
382 oxygen dimers (e.g. $^{32}\text{S}^+$ and $^{34}\text{S}^+$ are interfered among others by $^{16}\text{O}^{16}\text{O}^+$ and $^{16}\text{O}^{18}\text{O}^+$
383 respectively). On the other hand, ^{28}Si is interfered by $^{14}\text{N}^{2+}$. [38] Both are difficult interferences
384 because O and N are present in the plasma. In addition, N interference in Si detection may also
385 be due to nitrogen presence in the employed solvents (HNO_3 employed in the acid digestion of
386 the sample). [38] Moreover, it does not make sense to measure Si by ICP-MS considering that
387 the main part of Si is expected to be as insoluble silicates, which may not be completely dissolved
388 with the HNO_3 -HCl acid digestion employed in this work. Finally, Cl presents also a very high
389 ionization potential and thus present high limit of detection due to a low degree of ionization.
390 [39]

391 Moreover, for a correct determination of Si, a complete extraction of the retainer should be
392 conducted including HF in the acid digestion step. Thus, μ -EDXRF allows to avoid the
393 manipulation of this last acid. Even if the quantification of the three mentioned elements (S, Si
394 and Cl) by μ -EDXRF may not be as accurate as the obtained by ICP-MS, an estimation of their

395 concentration influencing the surfaces of the building can be obtained. In this sense, it must be
396 pointed out that this estimation is enough for the requirements of particles arriving to Cultural
397 Heritage, where an exact value is not really the point of the research. Finally, these elements,
398 S, Si and Cl, better determined by μ -EDXRF are widely present in atmospheric PM of a diffuse or
399 direct urban-industrial (S) and marine environments (Cl and S) and also due to the emissions of
400 crustal particles or those coming directly from beach sand (Si), and they play a key role in the
401 conservation state of building façades.

402 In the building considered in this work, the deposition of calcareous materials or
403 aluminosilicates may not be very harmful for its conservation. However, the deposition of the
404 more soluble NaCl or sulphates may add new ions that can be solubilised and enter the material
405 through its porous matrix, crystallizing on the surface or inside the material or reacting with its
406 original components. In addition, a high concentration of Fe metallic particles can trigger the
407 sulphating of the materials.

408 Although in this work, the main objective was to obtain information about the kind of
409 particles and their flux arriving to the façade of a construction, the same passive sampler could
410 also be extensively applied to other situations where PM characterisation is required, such as
411 air pollution control of a specific area.

412

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553

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

FIGURES

Figure S-1. A) Rigaku Ultra Carry Light sample retainer and B) Experiment location in Punta Begoña Galleries on the wall of the Lower Gallery.

Figure S-2. Selection of the circular area and the sum spectrum belonging to that specific circular area inside the whole square mapped area of one of the replicates of the PM retainer exposed for nine months in Punta Begoña (X9C).

TABLES

Table S-1. Elemental concentrations obtained by Fundamental Parameters for the 800 mm² circular area detected for the three replicates of the blank retainers.

Elements	Concentration (mg/kg)
Na	1130 ± 30
Mg	330 ± 2
Al	251 ± 8
Si	220 ± 10
Ca	140 ± 30
Ti	18 ± 3

Cr	10 ± 2
Mn	4.2 ± 0.8
Fe	11 ± 5
Cu	16 ± 1
Zn	72 ± 3